

D5.1

Data Management Plan

Responsible Partner: i2CAT

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Abstract

This document details the Data Management Plan for the MultiX project. The purpose of this deliverable is to define the output management plan (considering all different sorts of results from the project and not only data) to be used to keep track of all outputs of the project and make sure they follow findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR) principles.

Keywords

Data Management Plan, DMP, FAIR, results

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Dissemination level	
PU Public, fully open. e.g., website	✓
CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
SEN Confidential to MultiX project and Commission Services	

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Acronyms and definitions

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
6G-IA	6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Creative Commons
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DASH	Data Access and Security Hub
DMP	Data Management plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EA	Ethics Advisor
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEU	Horizon Europe
ID	Identifier
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MARCXML	Machine-Readable Cataloging XML

MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
ML	Machine Learning
MP6R	MultiX fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN
MP6RC	MultiX fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN controller
MPS	MultiX Perception System
NDT	Network Digital Twin
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
Pdf	Portable document format
PID	Persistent Identifier
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
RAN	Radio Access Network
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SW	Software
T	Task
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Table of partners

Short Name	Partner
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
APP	Apple Technology Engineering BV&CO KG
OTE	ORGANISMOS TILEPIKOINONION TIS ELLADOS OTE AE
INT	Intel Deutschland GmbH
IDE	InterDigital Europe LTD
NEC	NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH
NEC Italia	NEC Italia S.p.A.
SAG	Siemens AG
TSA	Telefónica S.A.
TID	Telefónica Innovación Digital
BR	BubbleRAN
NXW	Nextworks
CNIT	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni
UNIPD	Università degli Studi di Padova
I2CAT	Fundació Privada i2CAT, Internet i Innovació digital a Catalunya
IMDEA	Fundación IMDEA Networks
IHP	IHP - Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics
IASA	Institute of Accelerating Systems and Applications
KUL	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
UC	Universidad de Cantabria

1 Executive summary

This document is the first report from Work Package 5 (WP5) “Impact Creation and Standardization”, specifically related to Task 5.3 (T5.3) “Data Management and Open Data”.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the procedures and guidelines for managing data within the MultiX project. It establishes a framework for data collection, processing, storage, and dissemination, ensuring that data is managed effectively throughout the project lifecycle and beyond.

The DMP is designed to align with the principles of open science and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data, promoting transparency and maximizing the potential impact of MultiX research outputs.

This document details the strategies for data identification, storage, security, and sharing, including the use of appropriate tools and platforms. It also addresses intellectual property rights (IPR), ethical considerations, and the allocation of resources for data management. By adhering to these guidelines, MultiX will ensure the quality, integrity, and long-term preservation of the data created, while fostering collaboration and facilitating the reuse of valuable research outputs.

2 Introduction

This document outlines the DMP that will be followed throughout the MultiX project. The overall objective of MultiX is to revolutionize the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Radio Access Network (RAN) design and operation, by developing a pioneering MultiX fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN system (MP6R) that will support an integrated multi-sensor, multi-static, multi-band, and multi-technology paradigm to enable multi-sensorial perception for future 6G sensing applications. To achieve this, the MP6R builds on top of three innovation pillars: i) MultiX Perception System (MPS); ii) MP6R controller (MP6RC); and iii) Data Access and Security Hub (DASH). The proposed MP6R RAN design, and a set of other selected innovations, will be validated and demonstrated in two specific Proof-of-Concepts (PoCs) targeting Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4-5: PoC#1) Multi-layer Network Digital Twin (NDT) for Industrial Manufacturing, and PoC#2) Contact-free eHealth Monitoring at Home Environment.

Considering its scope and objectives, a relevant amount of data will be generated and reused during the project. The DMP establishes the rules and processes to ensure the correct management of such data during the project lifetime and beyond. It serves to ensure that data is preserved in its entirety and thus guarantees that there is no loss of information, facilitating its management from the moment it is produced until its final publication.

The DMP details the methodology to ensure that the generated data complies with the FAIR principles. To do so, the DMP aims to i) ensure proper documentation and accessibility of datasets generated within the project, ii) define best practices for storing, preserving, and sharing data, iii) facilitate collaboration among consortium partners through standardized data management procedures, and iv) support long-term sustainability and reusability of project outputs. To this end, MultiX follows the objectives of the Open Science Policy of the Horizon Europe (HEU) framework.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows:

Section 3 provides a general overview of the DMP, focusing on its purpose and the open science approach. Section 4 presents the data summary, explaining the expected types of data and the main format or volume. Section 5 details the FAIR principles adopted by MultiX, as well as recommendations on processes and actions to be followed to ensure proper data management. Section 6 analyses potential ethical risks, their management, related contingency plans, as well as data security mechanisms. Section 7 sets out the procedures that are being followed for the identification, description, and management of the data generated during the project lifetime. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section 8.

3 General Overview

3.1 Purpose: Open Research Europe and Open Science

MultiX completely adheres to the Open Science policy fostered by the EC. When HEU was initially launched (2021) it set a new standard for dissemination of knowledge across Europe. The challenge that was envisaged at that time was to embrace open science as the modus operandi for all researchers.

Open science strengthens sharing of knowledge, data and tools as early as possible in the Research and Innovation process, promoting an open collaboration with all relevant stakeholders, including academia, industry, public authorities, end users and society at large.

The following open science practices, identified by the EC, are particularly fostered during the MultiX project:

- Open access to research outputs, including publications, datasets, software (SW), algorithms, etc.
- Early and open sharing of research, including results discussed in the deliverables of the project and paper pre-preprints in public repositories.
- Use of open research infrastructures, promoting the use of Zenodo¹ to upload all project results.
- Open collaboration with the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) and the 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) working groups (WGs), promoting the publication of white papers in topics related to the project goals.

To facilitate an open access to research outputs, MultiX leverages the services provided by the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), as detailed in Section 5. Furthermore, MultiX also relies on other open access channels: i) the project website² is used to provide access to pre-print versions of accepted papers, as well as conference presentations; ii) the project social networks (X³, LinkedIn⁴, YouTube Channel⁵, Mastodon⁶ and BlueSky⁷) are being used to strengthen the visibility of the project results, with links to publications and presentations; iii) other open repositories, such as arXiv⁸, can be used for other outcomes.

¹ <https://zenodo.org>

² <https://multix-6g.eu/>

³ <https://x.com/MultiX6GProject>

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/multix-6g>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/@MultiX-6GProject>

⁶ <https://mastodon.social/@MultiX6GProject>

⁷ <https://bsky.app/profile/multix-6gproject.bsky.social>

⁸ <https://arxiv.org/>

MultiX has allocated resources to ensure an effective management of the Open science during the project lifetime, also thanks to the dedicated role of the Open science and Output manager (Prof. Ramon Agüero).

3.2 Monitoring and Updates

A specific project task (T5.4) ensures that the project outcomes adhere to the DMP plan, by continuously monitoring that the Open science goals are adopted during the project lifetime. This allows to early identify deviations and take the corresponding counter-measurements to revert them. Two additional reports, D5.3 and D5.4, will be delivered throughout the project lifetime, providing an analysis of application of the Open science measurements. Furthermore, major updates and situations that require specific actions are being managed by the Project Management Team, as specified in the Consortium Agreement.

Besides providing an update of the application of the Open science actions, the mentioned future deliverables will also include potential modifications. For instance, depicting new types of datasets, algorithms or models that may be generated by the research conducted in the different work packages.

It is important to highlight that it is the responsibility of each partner to ensure that the data generated is treated according to the procedures defined in the DMP.

4 Data Summary

4.1 Types of Data Generated and Used

At the time of writing, the information and data that we foresee to be generated by the MultiX consortium belong to the following types of data:

- Human-readable documents: project documentation, reports, deliverables, as well as scientific publications, white papers, presentations, standard contributions, etc. Most of them will use the Portable Document Format (pdf).
- Source code, including SW binary files: the implementation of the different functionalities, protocols, interfaces, algorithms, models, etc., that are being generated during the project lifetime.
- Experimental data: both raw and processed data coming from experiments.

Since Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML) techniques are used for some of the techniques that are proposed during the project lifespan, the generation of datasets to assess their behaviour is of the utmost relevance. In this sense, we shall distinguish between datasets used for training purposes and datasets that can be used to assess the performance of the corresponding solutions, evaluating the underlying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The different datasets that are being generated are uploaded in public repositories (most notably Zenodo), as detailed in Section 5, and a complete list (with the corresponding links) is made available following the MultiX Data Catalogue.

Regarding experimental data, we plan to both reuse existing data from other sources and generate new data sets. Regarding already available datasets, we plan to use existing datasets generated by partners of the MultiX consortium in the past as well as others coming from external sources, publicly available in different repositories.

4.2 Data Sources and Collection Methods

All data, regardless of the source, are being collected in a digital form. Each partner is responsible for the generated information. The project has deployed a sharing framework, based on the SharePoint technology, so that all information generated during the project lifetime can be shared with all consortium members in a secure and access-restricted place. Furthermore, all relevant outcomes are being stored at a public repository, ensuring their long-term preservation.

4.3 Expected Data Volume and Format

At the time being, it is not easy to envisage the volume of the data that will be generated during the project. However, it can be foreseen that some of the generated datasets may be rather large, since those are going to be exploited to train, and then to assess the AI/ML models that

will be developed during the project. Most of these datasets will be formatted as Comma Separated Values (csv) files, and stored in public repositories, together with the metadata required to appropriately use them. All the information will be stored following the MultiX Data Catalogue, as detailed in Section 5.

4.4 Data Ownership and Responsibilities

In general, documents generated during the project lifespan (reports, deliverables) are associated with MultiX, and there is no need to establish their ownership. A project internal server is used to store working copies of such documents, while final versions are uploaded in public repositories, ensuring their availability after the end of the project. The project coordinator has established a process to be followed, which also provides a link to such document in the public MultiX website.

Outcomes from the research conducted by individual partners in the scope of their participation in the MultiX project fall under the responsibility of the respective partner. An automated process has also been established, using a form in the project SharePoint. Once the version to be shared is uploaded in the open repository (Zenodo), the corresponding details are registered with such form, so that the information is accessible in the MultiX website.

Each partner that creates datasets and algorithms needs to keep a working version in the service of their choice (for instance, a git server). When a version is to be uploaded in the project server, the corresponding metadata needs to be generated and registered. The same partner has also to take care of updating the corresponding data/model/algorithm if a new version is to be shared, or when a major update has been made.

4.5 Other research outputs

While the processing and management of both documents (deliverables, papers, presentations, etc.) and datasets is more straightforward, MultiX will also produce algorithms and models, which will be made available as SW code. The Python language would be likely the preferred choice, but other alternatives are also possible, especially if they are integrated within existing tools or frameworks. Stable releases of such codes will be uploaded in a public repository (Zenodo), while the working copy will be kept in git servers, where the released versions will be also kept.

5 FAIR Data Approach

5.1 FAIR Principles

The MultiX project is committed to adhering to the FAIR principles to ensure that research data is managed effectively and can be widely reused. Following the approach promoted by the EC in its data strategy, which pursues and encourages a knowledge cloud fostered by open access data, MultiX aligns with the guidelines of the HEU programme and aims to make its data as open as possible. This commitment is based on the understanding that research projects like MultiX generate a large amount of data that requires proper management, storage, and processing to facilitate its use. As the scientific community is committed to Open science, a set of best practices for handling and publishing scientific data is essential.

The FAIR principles, as outlined in "The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship"⁹, emphasize that data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Findable means that data and its associated metadata should be easy to discover by both humans and machines. Accessible implies that data should be obtainable, though access may be subject to specific conditions. Interoperable signifies that data should be capable of working with other data, applications, or workflows. Reusable indicates that data should be utilized for new purposes, including further research, different applications, and commercial exploitation.

Embracing these principles is crucial for MultiX, which aims to align with the HEU Open science Policy, promoting transparency, fostering collaboration, and maximizing the impact of the research outcomes of the project. This DMP portrays how the publications, documents, SW, or datasets produced during the project lifetime are managed and treated following the FAIR principles.

5.2 MultiX Measures to Ensure FAIR Data

5.2.1 Making Data Findable

To ensure that the data produced by MultiX can be easily discovered and effectively utilized by all project stakeholders, e.g., researchers, industry partners, and policymakers, a robust approach to data findability is essential. This process begins with the assignment of persistent identifiers (PIDs) to all datasets (collection of data that pertains to a specific experiment/scenario/demonstration), ensuring that each dataset has a unique and citable reference. MultiX datasets need to be registered with Zenodo, (although other open science

⁹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

repositories such as OpenAIRE, can also be used), providing a structured environment where metadata and dataset records are openly accessible.

To enhance searchability and facilitate machine-readability, MultiX adheres to established metadata standards, such as Dublin Core¹⁰, DataCite¹¹, and OpenAIRE¹². These metadata schemas ensure that every dataset is systematically described with the required details, including title, authors, version, keywords, licensing, and access conditions. Additionally, metadata is being embedded in repositories using schema.org and JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data (JSON-LD) formats, allowing for seamless integration into Linked Data frameworks and automated discovery through research infrastructures.

To further enhance the discoverability of MultiX data, relevant keywords and tags are associated with datasets. These keywords are carefully selected to reflect the content, context, and key characteristics of the data, making it easier for users to find the data through keyword searches.

A key component of the findability strategy is the MultiX Data Catalogue, a centralized index where all datasets are listed, categorized, and version controlled. This catalogue is updated continuously, allowing both consortium members and external researchers to quickly locate and reference datasets based on specific search criteria. To standardize the dataset naming process, MultiX adopts a structured naming convention, which follows the pattern *MultiX_<DatasetType>_<Name>_<Partner>_<Date>_<Version>*, ensuring clarity, traceability, and consistency across different datasets, where

- [DatasetType] is the type of data (e.g., publication, code, design, experimental).
- [Name] is a short, characteristic name for the data. For experimental data, this may include a two-digit number to identify data generated by the same partner on the same day (e.g., 00, 01, 02...).
- [Partner] is the name of the organization associated with the dataset, using partner acronyms.
- [Date] is the date when the data was produced (format: YYYYMMDD).
- [Version] is the version number of the data.
- _ (underscore) is used as the separator between fields.

For example: *MultiX_experimental_data01_INSTITUTION_20250315_v2* would identify a dataset of experimental data, generated on March 15, 2025, by INSTITUTION, and in version 2.

¹⁰ <https://www.dublincore.org/>

¹¹ <https://datacite.org/>

¹² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

Moreover, MultiX might also integrate its datasets into major Open science platforms, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), further increasing their discoverability and interoperability with other European research initiatives. Where applicable, Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) might be developed to provide programmatic access to datasets, enabling third-party applications and research platforms to query, filter, and retrieve data efficiently.

By implementing these comprehensive strategies, MultiX ensures that its research data remains structured, well-documented, and readily discoverable, significantly enhancing the visibility, accessibility, and long-term impact of the scientific output of the project.

5.2.2 Making Data Accessible

MultiX is committed to ensuring that its research data is as accessible as possible, while carefully considering necessary restrictions and ethical considerations. The accessibility of MultiX data is defined by a clear and transparent set of conditions. Aligned with the project focus on open science, a significant portion of the data is being made available through open access. This commitment is underpinned using well-established repositories such as Zenodo. Zenodo is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. It is free to upload and free to access, making scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable, and discoverable for the long term. MultiX has already created a community within Zenodo¹³, and the results of the project (including publications) are being linked to it. Zenodo assigns all publicly available uploads a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make the upload easily and uniquely citable. Additionally, Zenodo supports harvesting of all content via the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)¹⁴, and all metadata is available under a Creative Commons (CC) license. The Zenodo platform is built on open-source foundations, and the code for Zenodo is itself open source, with ongoing development available for public contributions on GitHub. This commitment to open-source infrastructure aligns with MultiX dedication to openness and transparency.

However, it is recognized that access conditions may vary depending on the specific data. Factors influencing these conditions include data sensitivity, IPRs, ethical considerations, and potential embargo periods. Datasets containing potentially sensitive information, such as data related to specific applications or security considerations, may be subject to restricted access to protect privacy and confidentiality. Access restrictions may also be applied to safeguard IPRs, particularly in cases where data has commercial potential or is subject to patenting. Furthermore, ethical considerations, such as the need to protect personal data or ensure responsible use of AI and ML models, may necessitate certain access limitations. In

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/multix>

¹⁴ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

some instances, embargo periods may be implemented to allow project partners to publish initial findings before making the underlying data openly accessible. The length of the embargo period will be defined on a per-result basis. Currently, for the specific results that require it, we aim at defining an embargo time to allow protection of all results. The specific access conditions for each dataset will be clearly and comprehensively documented within the metadata of the dataset, ensuring transparency and clarity for potential users.

MultiX establishes transparent and well-defined procedures to facilitate access to project data. A substantial portion of the data is being made openly accessible through appropriate data repositories to broaden the dissemination and availability of results. The selection of these repositories is based on several key factors. Repositories are chosen for their reliability and trustworthiness, including their established reputation, robust long-term preservation policies, and adherence to relevant standards. Where appropriate, disciplinary relevance is prioritized, with domain-specific repositories favoured to ensure that data is accessible to the most relevant research communities. Repositories that strongly support open access principles are preferred to maximize data dissemination. MultiX also relies on complementary open access channels including: i) The release of pre-publication versions through the project website; ii) The release of paper presentations in conferences through the website; iii) The use of social media to provide links to publications and presentation files. Other kind of publications, for example, conference and workshop contributions, are provided with Open Access, likely through a *green* approach using, e.g., arXiv.org or other appropriate repositories. Similarly, deliverables produced by the project are also being archived in stable repositories, to ensure the long-term availability of the material. Archiving of the deliverables may be done with an embargo period, in coordination with the project officer.

In case some results (dataset, code, etc.) cannot be made public due to reasons mentioned earlier, metadata is generated and stored in Zenodo to be easily found, by identifying the contact person to further request them. Data is shared using standard formats. Currently, we do not foresee any need for specialized SW to access the data. Furthermore, any code generated by the MultiX project is released under open-source licenses. At the end of the project, a static copy of the project website, including information on open science activities, will be archived on stable servers to ensure the long-term preservation of project outputs. Finally, repositories that demonstrate compliance with relevant metadata standards are favoured to enhance data findability and interoperability.

Where applicable, MultiX utilizes standard communication protocols to facilitate data access and exchange. This may include the use of APIs to enable efficient programmatic access to data, promoting interoperability and facilitating data integration with other systems and applications.

5.2.3 Making Data Interoperable

Interoperability is a fundamental principle that MultiX embraces to ensure seamless data exchange and utilization across diverse systems, applications, and research communities. To achieve this, MultiX prioritizes the use of open and standardized data formats whenever feasible. This strategic choice facilitates the easy reading, processing, and exchange of data by various SW and systems. The selection of specific data formats is carefully considered, considering the unique characteristics of the data being generated and their widespread adoption within the relevant research domains. For instance, formats such as CSV for tabular data, JSON for structured data, Extensible Markup Language (XML) for data exchange, GeoJSON for geospatial data, and standard image and audio formats may be employed. A comprehensive record of the data formats utilized for each dataset is meticulously maintained and included within the metadata of the dataset, providing clarity and facilitating proper data handling. For instance, Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or Machine-Readable Cataloging XML (MARCXML). For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g., license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). We do not anticipate the use of any project-specific ontology or vocabulary.

Furthermore, the metadata standards selected by MultiX play a crucial role in fostering interoperability. By adhering to standardized metadata practices, the project establishes a common framework for describing data, simplifying the process for other systems and users to comprehend the context, structure, and meaning of data. This standardized approach is expected to significantly facilitate data exchange and integration with diverse datasets and systems, regardless of their origin or disciplinary focus.

5.2.4 Enhancing Data Reusability

Reusability forms a cornerstone of MultiX data management strategy, with a strong commitment to ensuring that data can be effectively leveraged for a broad range of purposes, spanning future research endeavors, further studies, and innovative applications. To foster and enhance data reusability, MultiX implements a series of key measures.

First and foremost, the project recognizes that clear and unambiguous data licensing is paramount to enabling seamless reuse. To this end, MultiX applies carefully selected and appropriate licenses to its datasets, providing explicit terms and conditions that govern how the data can be used, modified, and distributed. CC licenses, such as CC BY or CC BY-SA, are given strong consideration as a primary licensing option, given their widespread recognition and their well-established framework for granting permissions and setting necessary restrictions. The specific license applied to each individual dataset are clearly and prominently indicated within the metadata of the dataset, ensuring that all potential users are fully informed regarding their rights and obligations in relation to data usage.

Beyond licensing, MultiX places significant emphasis on the provision of comprehensive and high-quality data documentation, recognizing its crucial role in facilitating effective data reuse. To this end, MultiX provides detailed and thorough documentation for its datasets, encompassing several key elements. Rich and standardized metadata is provided, offering comprehensive descriptions of the context, origin, structure, and content of the data. Where applicable, data dictionaries are meticulously created to define the precise meaning and format of data elements within each dataset, providing clarity and facilitating accurate interpretation. For datasets that originate from surveys or questionnaires, detailed codebooks are provided, explaining the coding schemes employed for responses. Datasets are also accompanied by clear and concise README files, providing a valuable overview of the data, offering instructions for its effective use, and outlining any relevant caveats or limitations that users should be aware of.

Furthermore, MultiX recognizes the importance of providing detailed provenance information. Comprehensive information about the provenance of the data is meticulously recorded and made readily available. This includes detailed information about the data sources utilized, the specific data collection methods employed, the data processing steps undertaken, and any transformations applied to the data throughout its lifecycle. Providing this detailed provenance information empowers users to fully understand the origin and quality of the data, to assess its suitability for their intended reuse purposes.

MultiX is based on the concept of openness, and that vision can become reality only if open science (including open-source) policies are fully embraced. As such, the project default policy for sharing results is to make them as much public as possible. All non-confidential project results are being made available in Zenodo, which includes documentation on how to reuse the project results. To support the replication of experiments and enhance the impact of the datasets, the generated data is also being appropriately referenced in scientific publications.

MultiX establishes clear and well-defined procedures and responsibilities for the creation, maintenance, and timely updating of data documentation throughout the entire project lifecycle. All documentation is securely stored alongside the corresponding data within designated data repositories, ensuring that it remains easily accessible to users whenever needed.

Finally, MultiX is committed to implementing robust quality assurance procedures to ensure the ongoing reliability, accuracy, and consistency of its data. These procedures may include rigorous data validation checks, thorough data cleaning processes, and comprehensive data quality assessments. By prioritizing and ensuring that data is consistently of high quality, MultiX significantly enhances its value and maximizes its potential for effective reuse across a wide range of applications.

6 Data Security and Ethics

6.1 Compliance with GDPR and Ethical Considerations

MultiX ensures full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [GDPR-2016] and other relevant EU and national data protection laws. Furthermore, MultiX commits to take the European AI and Data act into consideration when developing technology. D5.2 [D5.2-2025] has more information on the next steps planned in MultiX on how to achieve that. Given the nature of the data collected, which may include health-related information (in particular, for PoC#2), adherence to these legal and ethical standards is essential to ensure the privacy, security, and rights of participants.

Key compliance measures include:

- **Legal Basis for Processing:** The processing of personal data is conducted under the principles of transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality. Participants are informed about data collection and processing through consent forms, ensuring transparency. Data collection is limited to what is strictly necessary, adhering to the proportionality principle of GDPR.
- **Data Subject Rights:** Participants have the right to access, rectify, and request the deletion of their personal data, in accordance with GDPR Articles 15-17. They are informed of these rights through project documentation and consent forms.
- **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA):** A DPIA is conducted to identify and mitigate risks associated with data collection. This includes ensuring compliance with GDPR principles such as data minimization, purpose limitation, and security. Two fixed evaluations will be conducted, one at the end of the first periodic report and another at the end of the project. In any case, if any issue arises, an ad hoc evaluation will be organized, and the results will be shared with the Consortium to modify the actions taken if necessary.
- **Informed Consent:** Before any data is collected, explicit informed consent needs to be obtained from participants to the activity that will generate that data. Participants are to be fully informed about the research purpose, data processing methods, and their rights, ensuring ethical integrity and transparency.
- **Ethical Oversight and Risk Management:** An Ethics Advisor (EA) (Amelia Andersdotter) has been appointed to monitor compliance and provide guidance. Ethical risks, including data privacy concerns and algorithmic bias, are actively managed with contingency plans in place.
- **Data Breach Protocol:** In the event of a data breach, the responsible parties have to notify relevant authorities and affected participants within 72 hours, as required by

GDPR. Measures have to be taken to contain and mitigate the breach, and a post-breach audit will be conducted to prevent future incidents.

- **Handling of Complaints:** Participants can submit complaints regarding data processing, which are to be addressed within 30 days, with the EA providing oversight where necessary.

By implementing these measures, MultiX ensures compliance with EU legal frameworks while upholding ethical integrity in research involving human participants.

6.2 Data Anonymization and Protection Measures

To safeguard participant privacy and secure personal data, the following anonymization and protection strategies are enforced:

- **Data Anonymization and Pseudonymization:** Identifiers such as names or student Identifiers (IDs) are removed or replaced with pseudonyms to prevent re-identification. Only authorized personnel can get access to re-identification keys if necessary.
- **Access Control Measures:** Role-based permissions are implemented, restricting data access to authorized personnel handling research data. Data is securely stored and shared only through authorized platforms.
- **Data Encryption:** All collected data is encrypted both in transit and at rest to ensure protection against unauthorized access and data breaches.
- **Storage and Retention Policies:** Data is securely stored following institutional and regulatory guidelines. Personally identifiable information is only retained for as long as necessary to fulfil research objectives. Data destruction has to follow GDPR compliance, ensuring complete and irreversible removal of sensitive information once the retention period expires.
- **Incident Response Plan:** In case of a data breach, a structured response protocol has to be followed, with immediate notification to the General Assembly. Actions include containment, resolution, and implementation of preventive measures.
- **Algorithmic Bias Prevention:** The project ensures that datasets used for research are diverse and representative to minimize bias in AI models. Regular audits and evaluations are conducted to detect and mitigate any unfair biases in data processing.

By integrating these security and anonymization measures, the project ensures the protection of participant data while maintaining compliance with GDPR and ethical research principles.

7 MultiX Data Management Procedures

This section summarizes how information and research outputs produced during the project lifespan are handled and managed, adhering to the policies and rules that were previously mentioned.

7.1 Storage and Access Control Mechanisms

An internal server has been set up, based on the SharePoint technology. All MultiX partners have access to such server, which is the main repository for the project execution. Access control is based on the specific technologies adopted by Microsoft, which include credentials based on user/password as well as Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA). The information stored in this server is internal to the project and its confidentiality is therefore ensured.

7.2 Data Sharing within the Consortium and External Parties

All outcomes produced within the project (except for those subject to potential intellectual property) will be made available to the community outside of the MultiX project and to interested stakeholders in a public Zenodo repository. Links to such documents will be included in the project website, and in some cases, we will use the project Social Networks to increase the visibility of some of the obtained results.

In addition, the consortium partners (for results they are responsible for) might decide to keep working copies of datasets and SW on their preferred server alternatives. In any case, stable releases are to be uploaded to the MultiX open repository (Zenodo).

7.3 Identification and update of datasets

As discussed in Section 5, MultiX fosters the FAIR principles. All datasets are named according to a certain nomenclature, which facilitate its identification, including information about the responsible partner, the version, etc.

The partner generating each dataset is responsible to update it as needed. All datasets and their updates are to be uploaded to the internal repository and all stable versions are to be made available through Zenodo.

7.4 Backup, and Disaster Recovery

There are two primary tools for storing the project's data and outcomes, ensuring robust backup and disaster recovery capabilities: i) the MultiX internal server, which utilizes SharePoint technology; and ii) Zenodo.

The SharePoint server is managed by the project coordinator (UC3M), which follows the strictest security protocols on its digital operations, complying with the current Spanish regulations in this regard. In addition, the whole server content is backed up daily, and the copies are stored at an out-of-premises server, through an encrypted connection and using a password-based storage. This ensures the security of data.

Zenodo, as an EC project, serves as a critical component of our data preservation and disaster recovery strategy. It is recognized as a fully Trusted Repository, adhering to all relevant security directives for data management, thereby providing a highly secure and independent off-site archive for publicly shareable project data.

7.5 Long-Term Data Preservation Strategy

One of the goals of the open science policy is to ensure the long-term preservation of all the project outcomes. In this sense, the servers that have been deployed have a sustainability policy that ensures that all data will be available after the project end.

Zenodo supports long-term preservation of all data, as the repository is projected to be maintained for the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, see Zenodo's Policies¹⁵. Furthermore, the project coordinator (UC3M), who is responsible of the server where the MultiX website is stored, ensures that it will be available, at least, for 10 years after the project end.

7.6 Allocation of Resources

MultiX has allocated resources to the management of the open science during its lifetime, through the figure of the Open science and Output manager (Prof. Ramón Agüero), who is constantly monitoring all the procedures and mechanisms that have been described in this document, ensuring that the project not only adheres to, but fosters open science goals.

Task 5.3 has been included in the MultiX work-plan to implement a continuous monitoring of the open science and output management, which ensures that all outcomes of the project are stored in a public repository, and that all policies and procedures are appropriately embraced. Furthermore, if any deviation or issue is detected, the corresponding counter-measurements

¹⁵ <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

is to be put in place. During the preparation phase, we asked all partners to have some resources allocated to such task, ensuring their engagement in the promotion of Open science.

8 Conclusion

The MultiX DMP serves as a comprehensive framework for managing the diverse data generated throughout the lifecycle of the project. The principles of open science and FAIR data have been central to the development of this plan, ensuring that all data generated by the MultiX project is not only managed effectively but also made widely accessible and reusable for the scientific community and other interested stakeholders. The DMP outlines clear procedures for data identification, storage, access control, sharing, and long-term preservation, all of which are essential for ensuring the integrity and longevity of the research outputs of project.

Key efforts have been made to ensure that data is managed following the FAIR concept, as per the HEU guidelines. The adoption of open science principles, including the use of trusted repositories like Zenodo, guarantees the transparency and sustainability of the project outcomes. These measures are expected to foster collaboration within the consortium and with external stakeholders.

The commitment to data security, compliance with GDPR, and ethical considerations ensures that sensitive information is protected and handled responsibly. The establishment of clear procedures for data sharing, regular monitoring of adherence to open science policies, and the allocation of dedicated resources for data management, guarantee that MultiX will continue to prioritize efficient and ethical data handling throughout its duration and beyond.

Looking forward, the successful implementation of the DMP will contribute to the long-term impact and legacy of the MultiX project, facilitating the reusability and continued development of its research findings. The integration of AI/ML models and experimental datasets will provide valuable insights that can drive innovations in future communication networks. Hence, MultiX strong commitment to make the data publicly available ensures that it can be leveraged for further research and development, increasing the visibility and impact of the project outcomes.

References

- [GDPR-2016] **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016** on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 119, 4 May 2016, pp. 1–88.
- [D5.2-2025] **MultiX, “D5.2: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Strategy Plan (CoDESP)”, Online: <https://multix-6g.eu/deliverables/>**